

Linguistic problems third culture kids face

Ismailova Dilrabo Xudoyberdi qizi

Master's degree student, Linguistic support of intercultural communication department, Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract:

Third culture kids (TCKs) are defined as children who have lived or interacted with two or more cultural environments for a significant portion of their developmental years. Levels, skills, and use of the inherited language of TCKs who return to their home country after falling into a second language environment can lead to difficulties. This article focuses on TCKs and the linguistic problems faced by the upon return to their home country.

Key words: third culture kids (TCKs, acculturation, inherited language

Children who have lived or interacted with a significant part of their developmental years in two or more cultural environments are defined as third culture kids (TCKs). The experience of TCK using English upon reentry to the United States was explored. These are children who have lived or interacted with two or more cultural environments for a significant portion of their developmental years. The terms expatriate kid and TCK are two interrelated concepts. As a child, they lived in different cultures and interacted with them. They differentiate TCKs from other expatriates according to the role of their parents' representation. TCK's parent works in a representational role whereas expatriates are not sponsored by their parents while they are abroad. The purpose of this article is to provide a broader definition of TCK and the linguistic problems of any child living in at least two countries abroad. This study is aimed at TCKs who have an inherited language of English, but they are fluent in the language of their host country to

the extent that it becomes their primary language.

It is difficult to estimate the number of American TCKs living far from their culture in the United States. These children grow up in different cultures and countries. Their parents could be military personnel, U.S. government officials, missionaries, businessmen, teachers, media workers, or those who have chosen to live abroad for a period of time. The United States Department of State recently estimated that 8.7 million Americans live abroad and many of them are raising children with plans to eventually return home (U.S. Department of State, 2015). As a result, millions of children who have spent part of their childhood years outside the United States, and most of them, may have been absorbed into the TCK.

Repatriation or return to home country from living in a foreign culture occurs when most TCKs return home with their families or for further education (Van Reken, 2012). Research has identified repatriation and re-adaptation as a major theme in the lives of TCKs. A return to home culture requires re-adaptation to language, trends, values, and school. The issue of their re-adjusting is complicated by a lack of information about them. This unrecognized diversity is referred to as “hidden diversity” and can manifest itself in different characteristics and attitudes due to having broader worldview, social, and academic experiences as compared to monocultural children (Pollock & Van Reken, 2009; Van Reken & Bethel, 2008). Pollock and Van Reken (2009) further explain the problem, “No one makes the same allowances for the ‘Third Culture Kid’ lack of knowledge or miscues as they would an obvious immigrant or recognized foreigner” (p.55). In addition, once TCKs are repatriated, there are several linguistic problems for them if the legislation is the language of the culture of their heritage. There is an outdated assumption that TCK can look at its home culture without linguistic problems again, it shows that the complexity and diversity of TCK.

Multilingualism is not without problems (Rydenvald, 2015). Loss of fluency in a legacy language and not knowing a specific vocabulary are two challenges for TCK (Pollock &

2

Van Reken, 2009). An additional problem for baptized TCKs is that this file can improve the development of inherited language skills (Pollock & Van Reken, 2009, p. 121). This will give them a language they are more familiar with than the English they inherited. In addition, baptized TCKs can repat hide through them because they look like their peers. (La Brack, 2012; Pollock & Van Reken, 2009; Van Reken, 2012).

The problem is that the heritage language experience, level of fluency and abilities of TCKs returning to their culture are unknown and may affect education due to an undefined gap in their language skills and competencies (Carhill, Suarez-Orozko and Paez) . , 2008; Polinskiy, 2011; Pollock and Van Reken, 2009). After repatriation to Japan, the problems with the heritage language of the Japanese TCKs were extensively studied, but baptized languages were poorly studied.

An experiment was conducted with a number of children who had returned to their homeland in America to study their linguistic problems. the conversation was in English and simple words were used throughout the conversation to make them better understood. One of the participants lived in Korea. When asked about his linguistic and cultural views, he replied, "How I speak depends on who I'm talking to. If I speak Korean, If someone talks to me in English then I would think in English. We can understand from this that TCKs do not mix two cultures but on the contrary they are aware of two cultures and can adapt depending on the context.

Although most TCKs are master s and post graduate degree, they lose self-confidence after returning to their homeland. The reason for this was that when they were studied, it was found that they did not know the heritage language well, did not

understand teachers' lectures during the lesson, or could not communicate their ideas correctly, sometimes lacking time to complete tasks.

They communicate and study in another language during childhood and upon

3

repatriation. But, while studying at a university or college, they are required to know the same academic language as their peers. This creates difficulties for them and cause to lose confidence in themselves. they complained that there is no problem in grammar but they have difficulty to writing essay in English and there is no good literature to teach writing structures.

Firstly, to address these issues, parents and teachers should encouraged and to read more resource using advanced vocabularies in the heritage language. Additionally, parents need to take into consideration what literature is common in that country schools to provide cultural literacy and vocabulary to make the transition to higher education easier. Secondly, Parents and educators of TCKs should deliver some type of basic instruction with plentiful practice on how to write an essay or lengthy paper for American standards before any return to the United States educational system. Third, the issues of shifts of language and identity require time to adjust to the new language and identity before TCKs returns to enter the United States educational system. Parents could companion their child to school in the United States earlier to provide this extra time. Educators could permit TCKs in the classroom extra time at the start of the school year to feel comfortable in the new environment. The fundamental and most important recommendation for all parents and educators of immersed TCKs is to consider the whole construct of the child. Shifting identities and elements of languages, their beliefs in knowing a language, are intertwined. Teachers and parents who pay special attention to any of these areas will solve some of the challenges for TCKs as soon as they enter the education system of their culture houses.

The difficulty in academic language, writing, lack of confidence, cycles of language proficiency, and shifting identities present a clearer picture of what the immersed TCKs' experiences upon returning home country. However, these challenges can often be hidden by their ability to communicate. It is important that families, educators, and transition specialists understand the challenges faced by TCCs returning to school in their own countries to address potential.

4

Immersed TCKs are unique individuals. The cultural identity of the TCKs is also a period of transition from one context to another. its structure resembles a chameleon that is constantly changing and varying in response to its environment.

Reference

Bikos, L., Kocheleva, J., King, D., Chang, G., McKenzie, A., Roenicke, C., Campbell, V., & Eckard, K.

(2009). A consensual qualitative investigation into the repatriation experiences of young adult, missionary kids. *Mental Health, Religion & Culture*, 12(7), 735-754.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13674670903032637>

Bylund, E., & Díaz, M. (2012). The effects of heritage language instruction on first language proficiency: A psycholinguistic perspective. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 15(5), 593–609.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2012.676620>

Carhill, A., Suarez-Orozco, C., & Paez, M. (2008). Explaining English language proficiency among adolescent immigrant students. *American Educational Research Journal*, 45(4), 1155–1179.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.3102/0002831208321443>

Cottrell, A. (2012). Explaining differences: TCKs and other CCKs, American and Japanese TCKs. In G. Bell-Villada, N. Sichel, F. Eidse, & E. Orr (Eds.), *Writing out of limbo: International childhoods, global nomads and third culture kids* (pp. 57–75).

Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars. Cummins, J. (2009). Putting language proficiency in its place: Responding to critiques of the conversational/academic language distinction. Retrieved from

https://moodle.csun.edu/pluginfile.php/2174625/mod_folder/content/0/BICS_CALP_Pu
[t](https://moodle.csun.edu/pluginfile.php/2174625/mod_folder/content/0/BICS_CALP_Pu)
[ing_Language_Proficiency_in_Its_Place_Jim_Cummins.pdf?forcedownload=1](https://moodle.csun.edu/pluginfile.php/2174625/mod_folder/content/0/BICS_CALP_Pu)
Davidson, D., & Lekic, M. (2013). The heritage and non-heritage learner in the overseas immersion context: Comparing learning outcomes and target-language utilization in the Russian flagship. *Heritage Language Journal*, 10(2), 88–114. Retrieved from <http://www.heritagelanguages.org>
Dewaele, J., & Van Oudenhoven, J. (2009). The effect of multilingualism/multiculturalism on